

ENGAGING TODAY'S MILLENNIALS USING CURRICULUM BASED ON CHEMICAL PRODUCT DESIGN

Sin-Moh CHEAH and Katerina YANG

Singapore Polytechnic

smcheah@sp.edu.sg

Abstract

This paper offers a curriculum model from the Diploma in Chemical Engineering of Singapore Polytechnic that takes on the challenge of providing an educational context to enhance engagement and meaning for many of our students, which are often referred to as the “millennials”. They are often depicted as very different in certain fundamental aspects as compared to students from previous generations. Specifically, the paper shares our approach in using the CDIO Framework (www.cdio.org) in designing a 3-year curriculum to meet this challenge. The approach is also applicable to other engineering programs seeking to re-design the curriculum for similar outcomes. It firstly summarizes the attributed characteristics of today’s millennials; and why a different curricular form and focus is necessary, with special emphasis on the context of chemical engineering education. Secondly, the “traditional” approach in chemical engineering education, which is based on chemical process plant design using computer simulation and modeling is outlined, and certain key limitations identified. We suggest that this approach is not particularly effective in engaging students in learning as no chemical plants actually get built. The paper then proposes that chemical engineering education should include the teaching of chemical product design in order to complement the teaching of process plant design. To develop the new curriculum, we introduced various “soft” skills into our diploma via two threads: one by integrating CDIO skills (such as teamwork, communication, thinking skills) in various core modules; and another by integrating C-D-I-O (conceiving, designing, implementing and operating) skills in creating innovative chemical products or systems as students’ final year capstone project. The result is a curriculum model that simultaneously delivers two important outcomes: a) students who are motivated to learn chemical engineering as they are able to apply that knowledge for the betterment of the less-privileged members of the community and; b) graduates who are desired by employers for their deep knowledge in chemical engineering and competency in chemical plant operations. This paper also emphasizes certain

unique features of the curriculum model highlighting examples of student projects with innovative chemical products.

Keywords: *chemical engineering, chemical product design, sustainable development, design thinking*

Introduction

Singapore Polytechnic (SP) has articulated its mission to be “a future ready institution that prepare our learners to be life ready, work ready and world ready”, and that its vision is to nurture “a caring community of inspired learners committed to serve with mastery.” These are most appropriate in positioning the institution to respond to today's fast changing world, where the purpose of education has evolved to better prepare students beyond classroom learning and the immediate working world. Education now needs also to equip students with knowledge, skills and attitudes essential for tackling the broader challenges of life in the 21st century.

This is especially important for today's students, often referred to as millennials, which approach their learning and have expectations quite differently from students of yesteryear. Millennials are generally framed as those born between 1982 and 2000, and are attributed to have “different” interests, goals, and learning preferences than students in the past (Taylor & Parsons, 2011). Millennials want to see relevance and meaning in what they are asked to learn and do, and they also like more immediate gratification and recognition - they need to feel like what they are doing is important and that they are on the right track, as perceived by them. Millennials also display a short attention span and are easily distracted. There is therefore a need to engage these students differently. Although he did not use the term millennials, Prensky (2005) refers to these students as those who “tune us out.” They live in a world that engages them differently than the world that we experienced. They find school much less interesting than the myriad of devices they carry in their pockets and backpacks. They are growing up in a world in which musicians, movie makers, TV stars, game designers, etc working very hard to earn their attention. When what is being offered isn’t engaging, these students truly resent their time being wasted. In more

and more of our schools, this group is quickly becoming the majority. Their possible motto, metaphorically speaking, is “Engage me or enrage me”, and they are “convinced that school is devoid of interest and totally irrelevant to their life” (Prensky, 2005).

Brief Review of Student Engagement

A thorough review of the topic of student engagement is beyond the scope of this paper, and has been provided by Trowler (2010). According to Harper & Quaye (2009), any attempt to engage students is an effort that goes beyond involvement or participation – it requires feelings and sense-making as well as activity. Acting without feeling engaged is just involvement or even compliance; feeling engaged without acting is dissociation. Fredricks, Blumenfeld & Paris (2004), identify three dimensions to student engagement, and we need to engage them on all these dimensions, as explained below:

1. Behavioral engagement: Students who are behaviorally engaged would typically comply with behavioral norms, such as attendance and involvement, and would demonstrate the absence of disruptive or negative behavior.
2. Emotional engagement: Students who engage emotionally would experience affective reactions such as interest, enjoyment, or a sense of belonging.
3. Cognitive engagement: Cognitively engaged students would be invested in their learning, would seek to go beyond the requirements, and would relish challenge.

Pinder-Grover & Groscurth (2009) noted that the most striking differences that millennials bring to the classroom are their preferences for *collaborating*, *connecting* and *creating social change* (italics in original), and cited many research studies supporting this claim. Kuh (2008) suggests using capstone courses and community-based projects to help students learn from one another and address social problems outside the classroom, noting that this approach is useful in achieving two essential learning goals. First, students learn to work and engage problems in the company of others, which means they must articulate their understandings, justify claims, and work together to solve problems. Second, students learn to deepen their understanding by listening to the insights of others, particularly those with backgrounds and experiences different from their own. These approaches form the guiding principles for our present effort.

Traditional and Revamped Chemical Engineering Education

Chemical engineering education had historically focused on the teaching of chemical process plant design, where students used simulation software to model a chemical processing plant to produce a given product of a certain purity based on some given raw material(s). Such a project is typically cast as final year capstone project, as it requires students to integrate

various core chemical engineering principles learnt in earlier years, such as fluid mechanics, heat and mass transfer, process control, etc. These subjects are taught as separate core modules, and students are often told: “not to worry, learn these first; they will be useful to you later in your design project.” The problem with this approach, besides not being particularly interesting and engaging for millennials, is the fact that no chemical processing plant is ever being built! Although such simulation exercise is useful in assessing students' ability to apply what they had learnt, it left students with a sense of “incompleteness” - whatever design they came up with may looked good on paper, but one can never really know.

In addition, traditional chemical engineering education, as for much of other engineering education curricula, has focused primarily on covering technical content, and failing to sufficiently incorporate the systematic infused teaching of soft skills such as teamwork and communication. This is typically relegated to the responsibility of faculty from the Language or Humanities schools. Issues such as ethics and other attitudinal or behavioral aspects are often not even included in the full-time curriculum programme.

Discussions of Work Done

The general framework for curriculum re-design based on CDIO is shown in Figure 1. The Singapore Polytechnic (SP) design thinking framework was added to complement CDIO, especially during the “conceive” stage. The design thinking approach focuses on three mutually supporting elements (Brown, 2009), namely that of user empathy (“What is desirable to users?”), technical feasibility (“What is possible with technology?”) and economic/business viability (“What is viable in the marketplace?”). This move is aimed at inculcating greater user empathy in our students during problem formulation, instead of diving straight into offering a solution that may not meet the requirements of the targeted user. This model allows us to design a curriculum that is able to effectively target all three aspects of student engagement: i.e. behaviorally, emotionally and cognitively. We believe this general framework is applicable to any discipline seeking to engage students in an effective manner.

Figure 1. General Framework integrating design thinking with CDIO

Based on the curriculum framework depicted in Figure 1, the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) Course Management Team formulated its own curriculum model for student engagement. Cheah (2008) previously provided a comprehensive account of the changes facing the chemical engineering industry and the education of chemical engineers; as well as the adoption of the CDIO Framework by DCHE to revamp its 3-year curriculum. Also, post this implementation period, further innovations and changes have been made based on pertinent feedback from evaluations (Cheah, Phua & Ng, 2013). A key change to note is the introduction of chemical product design (Cheah, 2010; Cheah & Ng, 2010) and design thinking (Cheah, 2012; Ng & Cheah, 2012, Chua & Cheah, 2013) into the curriculum, whereby students are encouraged to identify areas of needs where solutions are possible via applications of appropriate chemical engineering principles. Specifically, we introduced two new modules, one in Year 1 entitled *Introduction to Chemical Product Design*, and another in Year 2 entitled *Chemical Product Design & Development*. This serves to support the execution of Year 3 capstone *Final Year Project* where students can come up with innovative chemical products for the less fortunate at the bottom-of-the-pyramid. In our core modules, besides teaching students the application of chemical engineering principles in process and equipment design (i.e. the "traditional" approach), we also include applications to chemical product design. For example, in the Year 2 core module *Heat Transfer and Equipment*, our students not only learnt about applications of heat transfer theories to the design of heat exchangers used in virtually all chemical processing plants, which they use in their Year 3 *Plant Design Project*, they also used the same formulas and equations to the design of water heater or a solar cooker that can be used in the *Final Year Project*.

At the same time, we integrated selected "soft" skills into the curriculum, to better develop graduate with certain attributes (e.g., communication, teamwork and thinking skills) desired by the employers. This is achieved by two important threads as explained below:

- (a) Infusion of Parts 2 Personal and Professional Skills and Attributes of the CDIO Syllabus (such as critical and creative thinking, hypothesis testing, ethics, information literacy, etc) and Part 3 Interpersonal Skills of the CDIO Syllabus (teamwork and communication) into various core modules. Collectively we refer to these skills as "CDIO skills" and they are introduced via integrated learning experiences which are 3-4 hours of laboratory activities or assignments; which we termed "engineering practice" (Cheah & Yang, 2013).
- (b) Infusion of Part 4 Conceiving, Designing, Implementing and Operating Systems in the Enterprise and Societal Context, whereby skills in creating innovative chemical products or systems is introduced. We refer this as "C-D-I-O skills" to distinguish them from the "CDIO skills" mentioned in part (a). These C-D-I-O skills enable our students

to carry out chemical product design as fulfillment of the diploma's final year capstone project.

Figure 2 shows the revised DCHE curriculum model incorporating the integration of basic mathematics and sciences (chemistry, biology and physics) modules, core chemical engineering modules (such as fluid mechanics, heat transfer, separation processes, and chemical reaction engineering), and a selection of free electives in Year 3. This supports the development of chemical process design and chemical product design at the end of the 3-year diploma. Where appropriate, chemical product design is further integrated with chemical process design, in learning contexts that require students need to come up with a flow sheet of how the chemical product can be scaled-up for production.

Figure 2. DCHE model for engaging students in chemical product design

Also shown in Figure 2 is the integration of various CDIO skills (shown as curved arrows) such as teamwork and communication, critical and creative thinking, systems thinking, ethics, global mindset, etc into core modules in our curriculum. With CDIO as the basis of our curriculum design, our model therefore emphasizes not just on students being able to integrate their technical knowledge into their projects, but they are also able to consider the economic and societal impact of their design as well.

At this point, it is worth clarifying our notion of "chemical products or systems". This refers to "technology that uses chemical engineering principles" as defined by Shaeiwitz & Turton (2003), which we felt is more appropriate for the outcomes expected of our diploma-level students. We also clarify "innovative" outcome of our approach to mean engineering products and systems that are driven by social, environmental or sustainability issues; and add values to the community-in-need. In other words, anything that is new to the community is counted as innovation, even if similar products are available elsewhere or if the change is an incremental one. Some of these innovative products emerged from the capstone projects include waste-to-gas digester, seaweed-to-fertilizer, rain water harvesting system, insulation material from sugarcane bagasse, pedal-powered filtration unit, and floating toilet system. As will be illustrated later, some of these projects have already been successfully implemented or in process of

being implemented, both locally in Singapore and in various countries in the region, including Indonesia, Myanmar, Nepal and Cambodia.

Figure 1 also shows the use of appropriate technology to drive the “I” (implement) and “O” (operate) phases of CDIO – in delivering innovative chemical product design envisioned in our curriculum outcome. Appropriate technologies – a term attributed to Schumacher (1973) – are usually characterized as small scale, energy efficient, environmentally sound, labor-intensive, and controlled by the local community (Hazeltine & Bull, 1999). The core principle of appropriate technology is to include local communities in technology selection and development, innovation and implementation, all in an environmentally sustainable manner (Tharakan, 2006). Appropriate technologies are often perceived as “low tech” and unimportant, and not usually addressed in engineering education or university research (Sandekian et al., 2007). However, we felt that they are indeed very suitable at the diploma-level, as our students need not master a very high level of technical competencies at this level of study. The students, in fact, proved to be very capable to design and implement a workable product or system consistent with the needs of the poorer sections of the wider global community and within the goals of sustainable development (Chua & Cheah, 2013).

In addition, to further strengthen the three aspects of student engagement, we also linked the outcome of our curriculum model (Figure 2) to the ideals of sustainable development espoused in the Brundtland Report, which explained it as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (UN, 1987). Specifically, as shown in Figure 3, we draw parallels between the three circles of design thinking and three circles of sustainable development.

Figure 3. Relationship between elements of design and sustainable development

This mapping process (Figure 3) helped address a common problem in many initiatives aimed at addressing sustainable development issues: that they had been narrowly focused only on environmental issues (Kagawa, 2007; Segalas et al, 2010). Nagel et al (2012) had earlier suggested that both design and sustainability are not mutually exclusive, and that if we are to prepare our students to deal with the complex problems of sustainability, we must provide them with a

holistic education incorporating all contexts of sustainability. In terms of curriculum design, our model serves as a useful tool that explicitly emphasizes placing equal focus on all three aspect of sustainable development when designing chemical products.

We now share some case studies from recent student final year projects. These are necessarily brief. For more detailed discussion of work done, see the work of Oh & Yang (2014).

Case Study (1): Floatable Toilet System in Cambodia

In this project, our students designed a toilet system that can float on water for a community-in-need in rural Cambodia, which was under threat of poor sanitary condition due to frequent floods in the region, using existing toilet systems which are very rudimentary. The students visited the village several times, the first of which is to speak to the villagers, where they also applied design thinking methodology in order to ascertain the villagers’ needs. They then proceed with several iterations of the design back in Singapore and eventually developed a prototype that was tested in Cambodia. With the help of local craftsmen, the floatable toilet was largely constructed from bamboo, a locally available and renewable resource. Besides the floating structure, the team also designed a separation system that removes urine from faeces; an anaerobic digester to help convert the human waste into fertilizers, as well as a system to capture the biogas was produced to be used as fuel. Subsequent visits included gathering feedback from the villagers and making improvements to the system. They also include training for the villagers in using the new system.

Figure 4. Conceptual Design of Floating Toilet and Portion of the Actual Prototype

Case Study (2): Herbal Soap Production in India

In this project, our students developed a suitable formulation to produce herbal soap using locally available natural resources in Sikkim, India such as sunflower oil, coconut oil, mint and lemongrass. The Yuksam community in Sikkim planted and harvested cardamom to earn a living. A few years ago, a disease struck the cardamom plants and wiped out the entire plantation. The villagers suffered a massive loss of income. Through empathy studies and interviews with the local community, several ideas were conceptualized such as paper and soap making. After several rounds of communication with the local community, it was found

that there was another organization aiding them in a project involving paper making. Hence, our students embarked on soap making, developed a suitable formulation, and renamed it as 'herbal soap' because it utilized plant-based ingredients. This project is still ongoing. The next phase of this project is to explore sustainable processes and technology that is suitable to be implemented at Sikkim to produce the herbal soap in larger amounts.

Case Study (3): Pavement Bricks for the Philippines

In this project, our students conducted a feasibility study of converting solid waste into usable and valuable product. In particular, the study focuses on Las Pinas, Metro Manila Philippines, which is one of the densest cities in the world. Newly migrant families live in makeshift squatters, with poor sanitation and environment in the city's dumpsite. A major concern for this community is the lack of proper regular jobs and disposable income. In addition, within the improvisational community, sandbags were used as a substitute to lie on the muddy grounds as walkways. During the monsoon season, flooding in the slums resulted in the sandbags being washed away. Replacement of sandbags is expensive and tedious. Our students formulated a paving brick to replace sand bags; using plastic waste, coffee grounds and gravels all available from the dumpsite. The paving brick prototype was tested by an independent external party, where it passed all the requirements of various applicable Standards.

Figure 6. Pavement Bricks from Waste Materials

Discussions

The curriculum model presented in Figure 1 allow us to directly engage students in all three aspects of cognitive (head), psychomotor (hand) and affective (heart) domains of learning that will allow

transformative learning to occur (Sipos et al., 2008). Working on sustainability-themed chemical product design projects provided the students with opportunities to connect and collaborate with real people from community-in-need, to solve real-world social or environmental problems using knowledge gained in class, facilitated a high level of self-efficacy for our students (Wals and Jickling, 2002). This, in turn, encourages their motivation and engagement for further learning, hopefully resulting in better attainment overall in the longer term. At present, we only have anecdotal evidence on this, as we did not conduct a course-wide evaluation on our students. Conversations with our students who took part in these sustainability-themed capstone projects suggested that most experienced a high level of engagement in these projects. Many noted that working on such projects had been an eye-opener and an enriching experience for them, and they are now more inspired to make a difference to the less fortunate using their knowledge. They also noted that they are now more appreciative of what they have and not to take things for granted. However, it is probably too early to tell if long-term transformative changes in students' attitudes, values or behavior as envisioned by Elliott (2010) had indeed taken place as we have not yet carried out any formal study on the impact of such curriculum re-orientation.

Conclusions

We have shared a curriculum model built around chemical product design which is able to meet the demands of both employers and students generally referred to as millennials. The curriculum is designed using the CDIO Framework supported by design thinking in the "Conceive" and "Design" phases, and utilizes appropriate technology to realize the "Implement" and "Operate" phases respectively. It is able to effectively engage millennials in their studies and deliver on the "traditional mandate" of our polytechnic education, which is to prepare graduates for the industry.

Acknowledgement

The author is indebted to Mr. Dennis Sale, Senior Education Advisor of Singapore Polytechnic for his review and constructive comments on this paper.

References

- Brown, T. (2009). *Change by Design: How Design Thinking Transforms Organizations and Inspires Innovation*, HarperBusiness.
- Cheah, S.M. (2008). Revamping the Diploma in Chemical Engineering Curriculum: Issues and Challenges, *Proc of the 2nd International Symposium on Advances in Technology Education*; Sep 9-11; Kumamoto, Japan

- Cheah, S.M. (2010). Chemical Product Design and Development: Learning from Student Experience, *Proc of the 4th International Symposium on Advances in Technology Education*; Sep 28-30; Kagoshima, Japan
- Cheah, S.M. (2012). Learning Points from Executing a Final Year Project Enhanced with Design Thinking, *Proc of the 6th International Symposium on Advances in Technology Education*; Sep 19-21; Kitakyushu, Japan
- Cheah, S.M., & Ng H.T. (2010). Product Design and Development for Chemical Engineering: Issues and Challenges. *Proc of the 6th International CDIO Conference*. Montréal, Canada.
- Cheah, S.M., Phua, S.T. & Ng, H.T. (2013). The Chemical Engineering CDIO Experience after 5 Years of Implementation, *Proc of the 9th International CDIO Conference*, MIT, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA
- Cheah, S.M., & Yang, K. (2013). Teaching Engineering Practice in Chemical Engineering via Experiential Learning, *Proc of the 7th International Symposium on Advances in Technology Education*; Sep 25-27; Nara, Japan
- Chua, P.H., & Cheah, S.M. (2013). Education for Sustainable Development using Design Thinking and Appropriate Technology. *Proc of the 9th International CDIO Conference*. Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA
- Elliott, J. (2010). Insights to Transformative Learning through Education for Sustainable Development. *Learning and Teaching in Higher Education*, 5, 96-113.
- Fredricks, J.A., Blumenfeld, P.C., & Paris, A.H. (2004). School Engagement: Potential of the Concept, State of the Evidence. *Review of Educ. Res.*, 74(1), pp.59-109
- Harper, S.R., & Quaye, S.J. (2009). Beyond Sameness, with Engagement and Outcomes for All, in *Student Engagement in Higher Education*, New York and London: Routledge
- Kagawa, F. (2007). Dissonance in Students' Perceptions of Sustainable Development and Sustainability: Implications for Curriculum Change. *Int. J. Sustain. High. Educ.*, 8, 317-338.
- Kuh, G.D. (2008). High-impact Educational Practices: What they are, Who has access to them, and why they matter, Washington, DC: Association of American Colleges and Universities
- Nagel, R.L., Papas, E.C., & Pierrakos, O. (2012). On a Vision to Educating Students in Sustainability and Design – The James Madison University School of Engineering Approach, *Sustainability*, 4, 72-91.
- Ng, H.T., & Cheah, S.M. (2012). Chemical Product Engineering using CDIO Enhanced with Design Thinking. *Proc of the 8th International CDIO Conference*. Brisbane, Australia.
- Oh, A.Y., & Yang, K. (2014). A Gift of Drinking Water: A Chemical Engineering CDIO Project, *Proc of the 8th International Symposium on Advances in Technology Education*; Sep 24-26; Singapore
- Prensky, M. (2005). Engage Me or Enrage Me: What Today's Learners Demand, *EDUCAUSE Review*, v40 n5 pp.60, 62, 64
- Pinder-Grover, T. & Groscurth, C.R. (2009). Principles for Teaching the Millennial Generation: Innovative Practices of U-M Faculty, *CRLT Occasional Paper No.26*, The University of Michigan,
- Sandekian, R., Amadei, B., Bielefeldt, A., & Summers, R.S. (2007). Engineering for Poverty Reduction: Challenges and Opportunities. *5th Latin American and Caribbean Conference for Engineering and Technology*, Tampico, Mexico.
- Schumacher E.F. (1973). *Small is Beautiful: Economics as if People Mattered*. Blond & Briggs Ltd, London.
- Segalas, J., Ferrer-Balas, D., & Muller, K.F. (2010). What Do Engineering Students Learn in Sustainability Courses? The Effect of the Pedagogical Approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 18, 275-284.
- Shaeiwitz, J.A., & Turton, R. (2003). Educating Chemical Engineers in Product Design, *Int. J. Engng Ed*, 19(1), 153-157.
- Sipos, Y., Battisti, B., & Grimm, K. (2008). Achieving Transformative Sustainability Learning: Engaging Head, Hands and Heart. *Int. J. Sustain. High. Educ.*, 9(1), 68-86.
- Tharakan, J. (2006). Educating Engineers in Appropriate Technology for Development. *9th UICEE Ann. Conf. on Eng. Educ.*, Muscat, Oman.
- Taylor, L. & Parsons, J. (2011). Improving Student Engagement, *Current Issues in Education*, 14(1)
- Trowler, V. (2010). Student Engagement Literature Review, The Higher Education Academy, UK.
- UN (1987). "Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development." United Nations General Assembly Resolution 42/187, 11 December 1987. Retrieved: 2007-04-12
- Wals, A.E.J. & Jickling, B. (2002). Sustainability in Higher Education: From Doublethink and Newspeak to Critical Thinking and Meaningful Learning. *Int. J. Sustain. High. Educ.*, 3(3), 221-232